

Critical Review on *Rasaprakash Sudhakara*: A Pharmaceutical Book

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ABSTRACT

Ayurveda has been called life science. It's mentioned in *Ayurveda* that by living a complete prosperous, happy life and achieving the salvation in the end is the ultimate goal of life. To filling the fulfillment of these objective *Rasa shastra* has emerged in *Ayurveda*. Through chronology, there were many disciplines of *Rasa shastra*, who through thousands of year of libration remained nonexistent and remained absorbed in the spiritual practice. The seers were *Nagarjuna*, *Vyadi*, *Nandi*, *Gorakshnath* etc. among them who wrote many books of *Rasa shastra*. *Rasaprakash sudhakara* is important books which focus upon two important theories i.e. *Lohavada* and *Chikitsavada*.

Keywords: *Rasa shastra*, *Lohavada*, *Chikitsavada*,
Dhatu, *Shodhana*, *Marana*

INTRODUCTION

Among the *Rasa granthas* *Rasaprakash sudhakara* is an important book, which is written by *Acharya Shri Yasodhar Bhatta* in 13th century AD. He lives in district Junagargh of Gujrat state and his father name is Pt. *Shri Padmnabha Bhatta* who belongs to Gouda Brahmana kula. *Acharya Yasodhar Bhatta* do not mentioned the name of his guru anywhere, while He quoted the name of *Acharya Somadeva* many times so

it may be possible that He is his master (Guru). *Rasaprakash sudhakara* was published two times by two *Acharya*, Firstly by *Acharya Yadava ji Trikam ji* in 1910 and secondary by *Acharya Jivaram Kalidash* in 1923. It is mentioned that this text is written in 13th centaury so it is more Authentic well arranged and development then other books. Here its review on the hindi commentry *Siddhiprada* of *Rasaprakash sudhakara* by *Acharya Siddhinandan mishra* published by *chauhambha orientalia varanasi* reprinted in 2013. *Acharya* started his texts from *Manglacharana* and at the end of his treatise describes his offspring. *Rasaprakash sudhakara* consist of 13 chapters (*Adhyaya*).

First Adhyaya

First chapter starts with *Mnglacharana* which included the prayer to *Lord Shiva*, *Sarswati vandana*, *Lord Ganesha*, and *Parada vandana*. Its consist of texts index, origin of mercury and its importance in details. 18 *sanskar* of *Parada* are given such as *Swedana*, *Mardana*, *Murchhana*, *Utthapana*, *Patana*, *Rodhana*, *Niyamana*, *Deepana*, *Abhraka Grasamana*, *Abhraka Charana*, *Garbhdruti*, *Bahyadruti*, *Jaarana*, *Ranjana*, *Saarana*, *Kramana*, *Vedhakarma*, and

Sevana sanskar in details and also mentioned the five type of *parada* dosh such as *Mala, Visha, Vahni, Mada, Darpa* along with its harmful effects. The first 8 *sanskar* for *Chikitsavada*, rest 10 for *Lohavada* and *dehavada*.

Second Adhyaya

Second chapter mentioned 4 type of *parada bandha*, such as *Jalauka bandh, Khota bandha, Paat bandha and Bhasma bandha*. Explain four type of remedial measure such as *Mulika (Plant), Mani, Gold, and Puti louh (Naga, Vanga)*. Five type of *Mulika bandha*, two type of *Vajra bandha* and five type of *Dhatu bandha* etc. Of *parada* in which *Mulika* is best, while *Mani* is medium, *Gold* is low and *puti louh* is consider as very low.

Third Adhyaya

Third chapter comprises four type of *Parada Bhasma* on the basis of color such as white (*sweta*), Black (*Krishna*), Yellowish (*Peeta*), and Blood Red (*Rakta*). Mention the extraction of *parada* from *Hingula*, method of preparation of white *bhasma* of *parada* as *Rasa karpur vidhi*, Red *bhasma* of *parada* as *Rasa sindoor* and *manikya* color of *bhasma* as *Rasa manikya*. Explain the *shadguna Gandhaka Jaarana, Rasa pottali and two type of Rasa parpatti*.

Fourth Adhyaya

Forth chapter represent eight metals in which four are *suddha louha* as Gold, Silver, Copper and Iron, two are *putilouh as Naaga, Vanga* and three are *Mishra louha* as Kashyam, Pittala and *Varta*, on calculation total nine metal but Author wrongly told eight in number. Explain the Type, *Shodhan, Marana*, and uses of all *Dhatu*. Four type of *Swarna marana*, two type of *Rajata marana*, four type of copper *marana*, three type of *louha marana* and two type of *Vanga and Naaga marana*.

Fifth Adhyaya

Fifth chapter comprises eight *Maharasa* such as *Abhraka, Kharpar, Vaikrant, Makshika, Vimala, Shasyaka, Silajit and Rajavart*. Explain the type,

properties, defects, *shodhana, marana, satva niskasana* of eight *maharasa*. Also explain three type of *Abhraka marana* and two type of *Abhraka satvapatana*.

Sixth Adhyaya

Sixth chapter deals with eight type of *Uprasa* such as *Hartal, Manahshila, Gandhaka, Fitkiri, Kankustha, Gairika, Anjana and Kashis*. Explain the type, *Shodhana*, Properties, defects, *Marana Satvapatana* and uses of *Uprasa*. Rest parts of this chapter explain the *Sadharana Rasa* as *Navsadar, Varatika, Amber, Girisindoor, Hingula, Mridarshringa*. Lastly explain the *shodhana* of all *Sadharan Rasa* by Triturating (*Bhavana*) three times in *Bijaura nimbu*.

Sevanth Adhyaya

Seventh chapter comprises Nine type of *Ratna* and there relation with the nine *Graha*. Explain Type, Properties and Defects of *Ratna*. Focus on Type of *Sodhana, Marana* and some combination of *Hira Bhasma*. Lastly explain the *marana* of all *Ratna, Ratna drutividhan and Ratna druti Lakshana*.

Eighth Adhyaya

Eighth chapter comprises hundred *Rasa Yoga* which are useful in curing the different diseases, such as Three type of *Jwarankush Rasa*, Five type of *Jwarari Rasa*, Three type of *pandu nasana Rasa*, Two type of *Hemgarbh pottali Rasa*, Two type of *Panchvaktro Rasa, Kanaka sundar Rasa, Atisar Bhairavi Guti, Grahni Kapat Rasa, Ichhabhedi Rasa, Swachhand Bhairava Rasa, Talkeshwar Rasa, Agni tundi Vati, Soolgaj Keshri Rasa, Kamdeva Rasa, Khechri Gutika* etc. Here *Acharya* mentioned tht all Hundred *Yoga* are collected from different *Rasa granthas* and maximum formulation are used on own experiencing. The intelligent *Vaidya*, used these carefully, to make them popular and respectful in the kingdom.

Ninth Adhyaya

Ninth chapter deals with sixty four Types of *Divya Aushadhi*. Name of *Divya Aushadhi*, so strange and maximum not in use, because the writer was from

district Junagarh of Gujrat state. He used mostly the local name of drug. Explain sixty eighth *Rasa Aushadhi* which are used in the *Jarana, Marana* and *Niyaman* of the *Parada*. Also explain sixty eighth *Maha Aushadhi*, in which maximum are controversial. In the last of this chapter He explains sixty eighth *Siddh Aushadhi* for *siddhi of Parada* i.e. *Lohasiddhi* and *Deha siddhi*.

Tenth Adhyaya

Tenth chapter consist of thirty nine *yantra* which is used for different purposes such as *Shodhana, Marana* and other process by which we control the *parada*. Here Author only give the name of *Yantra* but not explain it. Explain fifteen type of *Musha* with six synonym of *musha* like *Musha, Kumudika, Koshthika, Karhatika, Patani* and *Vahnimitra*. Explain four type of *Koshthi* and its uses and also explain the *Putra*, its type, size and lastly the synonyms of *putra* as *Upal, Pistak, Chhana, Utpala, Girindaka, Chhagana, Upalasaari* and *Gobar*.

Eleventh Adhyaya

Eleventh chapter comprises the wondrous miracle of metal i.e. the process of colorings the metals. It explains the twenty different procedures of *Hemkarana*, Seventeen procedure of *Roupya karana*, Artificial *Moti* preparation and how to make a large size of *Moti* from small one. Lastly at the end of the chapter explain the process of Artificial *Praval* making.

Twelfth Adhyaya

Twelfth chapter deals with different type of *Vajikaraka* formulation as *Vaajikari Gutika* and four type of *Vajikaro leha*.

Thirteen Adhyaya

Thirteen chapter deals four type of formulation of *Veerya sthambhan* as *Veerya sthambhaka vatika, Lepa* and *shukra sthambhaka churna*. Lastly of the book the Author explain about his offspring.

Unique feature of the book

In *Rasaprakash sudhakar* the origin of *Parada* is given and how the *parada* fallow beautiful girls (*shodassheeya*). He explains five type of *Dosha* as *Visha, Vahni, Mala, Mada* and *Darpa* in which *Mada* and *Darpa* is unique and in *Saptkanchuka Dosha Louha* and *Tamraj* is unique. In *Rasa prakash sudhakar* only four type of *Parada bandh* is given i.e. *Jalauka, Khota, Paata* and *Bhasma bandh*. Collection of special Hundred *Rasa yoga*, in which maximum is experienced by the Author. *Guhya yantra, Gandhpista yantra, Deva yantra* and *Ghanika yantra* which explanation are not found anywhere.

CONCLUSION

Rasaprakash sudhakar is a unique *Grantha* of pharmaceutical preparation of *Rasa yoga* which mainly focus upon *Lohavada* and *Chikitsavada*. The book is written by *Acharya Yashodhar Bhatta* in 13th century who belongs from district Junagargh of Gujrat state. This book consist of thirteen chapters starts from *Manglacharana* with prayer of Lord *Shiva, Saraswati, Ganesha* and *Parada*. Explain origin, Eighteen *Sanskar*, and four type of *Prada bandha* such as *Jalauka, Khota, Paata* and *Bhasma bandh*. Explain four type of special *Parada bhasma* on the basis of its color as White, Black, Yellowish and Blood red. Deals with *Shodhana, Marana* etc. of *Asthadhatu*. Completely explain the *Maharasa, Uprasa* its types, uses and properties in detail. Deals with *Navaratna* and its relation with *Navagraha*. Explain Hundred *Rasa yoga* which is collected and experienced by the Author himself. It also mentioned sixty four Types of *Divya Aushadhi*, sixty eighth types of *Rasa Aushadhi, Maha Aushadhi* and *Siddh Ausadhi* which mostly contain the controversial drugs. Thirty nine type of *Yantra*, Fifteen type of *Musha*, Four type of *Kosthi* are explained which are used for different process such as *Shodhan, Marana* etc. of *parada* and other metals. Deals with the *puts* and its type, size and synonyms of *puta* etc. It's explained the artificial preparation of *Swarna* as twenty type of *Hemkarana*, Seventeen type of *Roupyakarana* and also explains the artificial preparation of *mukta* and *praval*. Deals with the formulation of *Vajikarana* and *Veerya*

stambhan and lastly *Acharya* explain about his offspring.

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